

NullSphere: A Unified Platform for Technical Interview Preparation

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Abstract

Software development is growing rapidly as a career path and more individuals are preparing for technical interviews. While multiple platforms exist to support, each platform solves only specific aspects such as coding practice, articles, interview experiences or structured roadmaps. This fragmentation forces learners to visit multiple platforms simultaneously, breaking focus and adding unnecessary overhead to their preparation. This study compares six interview preparation platforms based on learning resources, interview experiences, communities, and structured roadmaps. A preliminary user survey (N = 14) was conducted to validate fragmentation as a primary issue. Platform evaluation was conducted through hands-on usage and qualitative analysis. Platform fragmentation was confirmed as the primary gap in the current ecosystem, with 78.6% of surveyed users relying on three or more platforms simultaneously, and 78.6% reporting difficulty tracking progress across them. Content availability is not the core issue; rather, the lack of integration between preparation components creates inefficiency. To address this, NullSphere is proposed as a unified platform integrating learning resources, structured roadmaps, a topic-wise question bank, an interview experience repository, and community interaction in a single system. The platform was publicly deployed and monitored over a 28-day period, gaining 200 active users, over 1,100 page views, and an average engagement time of 1 minute 20 seconds across users from six countries, demonstrating its viability as a unified interview preparation solution.

Keywords: technical interview preparation; integrated learning platform; developer education; platform fragmentation; learning roadmaps; AI-assisted learning; community-driven learning; e-learning systems

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

Over time, the preparation landscape for software development roles has expanded rapidly. Multiple platforms have emerged to provide practice and learning resources for individuals preparing for technical roles. These platforms offer different types of preparation support, including coding questions, tutorials, interview experiences, and learning roadmaps. While each is helpful individually, they operate in isolation from one another.

1.2. Problem Statement

Despite the availability of multiple platforms, the primary issue lies in their lack of integration. Most platforms provide individual solutions, creating a distributed system in which users must frequently switch between different tools to complete their preparation. This switching reduces efficiency, disrupts learning flow, and makes it difficult to track and manage progress in a cohesive manner.

1.3. Objectives

The objectives of this study are:

- To research existing technical preparation platforms
- To compare their features and services
- To identify gaps in the current ecosystem
- To propose an integrated platform as a solution

1.4. Contribution of the Study

This paper provides a structured comparison of multiple learning platforms based on key factors required for interview preparation, including resources, interview support, and community features. It highlights the issue of platform fragmentation and introduces NullSphere as a unified solution that consolidates all these resources into a single system.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Selection of Platforms

Six platforms were selected to represent the primary categories of tools commonly encountered during technical interview preparation. These cover coding practice, conceptual learning, roadmap guidance, community experience sharing, and production-level skill building. The selected platforms are: Code360 by Coding Ninjas, LeetCode, GeeksforGeeks, Codecrafters.io, roadmap.sh, and Glassdoor.

2.2. Evaluation Criteria

The platforms were reviewed and compared across four dimensions that collectively represent the complete preparation journey of a learner:

- Learning Resources
- Interview Preparation Support
- Community Support
- Structured Roadmaps

2.3. Approach to Analysis

Platform evaluation was conducted through hands-on usage during the researcher's technical interview preparation. Each platform was assessed by exploring its learning resources, practice problems, and community and roadmap features. Since the analysis is based on practical usage rather than controlled experiments, the findings are qualitative and reflect the perspective of an active learner. This approach captures usability challenges often missed in feature-based comparisons alone.

2.4. User Survey Design

To validate the fragmentation problem and evaluate NullSphere, a preliminary user survey was conducted with $N = 14$ participants recruited from the platform's user base during the 28-day deployment period. The survey comprised three parts:

Part A assessed current preparation habits and fragmentation experience

Part B evaluated NullSphere across six dimensions on a 1-5 scale

Part C collected demographic context. Participation was voluntary and anonymous.

Given the sample size, findings are treated as preliminary and exploratory rather than statistically generalizable.

3. Literature Review

The current learning ecosystem encompasses multiple platforms, each of which addresses a specific aspect of technical interview preparation. Coding-based platforms primarily enhance problem-solving abilities through large banks of practice questions. While widely used for interview preparation, these platforms do not provide adequate guidance for beginners seeking a well-organized learning process [3,4].

Learning-focused systems offer elaborate descriptions of concepts through articles, tutorials, and examples. These platforms assist users in acquiring theoretical knowledge, though they typically lack sufficient practice exposure [5]. Community-based platforms enable users to exchange experiences and gain insights from one another. While offering real-world information, such platforms are generally unstructured and rely heavily on user-generated content [8].

Roadmap-based platforms provide structured guidance on the sequence in which content should be learned. They are particularly beneficial for new entrants, but typically do not incorporate interview questions or interview-specific advice [7]. Company insight platforms offer data on salaries, recruitment trends, and interview experiences, providing useful context, but lack formal learning and preparation resources [8].

Collectively, while each platform category is valuable, none provides a complete solution. This creates a discontinuity in the ecosystem in which users must integrate multiple platforms to meet their preparation goals. No prior work has proposed a unified, integrated platform that consolidates all components of the technical interview preparation workflow.

Table 1. Comparison of existing technical interview preparation platforms.

Platform	Primary Focus	Key Features	Strengths	Limitations
Code360 (Coding Ninjas) [3]	Structured coding preparation	DSA sheets, guided paths, coding problems, contests	Structured curriculum, beginner-friendly	Limited real interview experience integration, no resume intelligence, less personalization
LeetCode [4]	DSA practice	Coding problems, contests, company tags	Strong DSA coverage, widely adopted	Lacks structured learning roadmap, resume intelligence, and production-level case studies

Platform	Primary Focus	Key Features	Strengths	Limitations
GeeksforGeeks [5]	Concept explanations & coding practice	Articles, tutorials, interview questions	Broad topic coverage	Content fragmentation, limited personalization, no AI-driven guidance
Codecrafters.io [6]	Hands-on system building	System design learning platform	Strong production-level exposure	Not interview-focused; no resume or community ecosystem
roadmap.sh [7]	Visual tech learning roadmaps	Role-based roadmap diagrams	Clear visual learning paths	Static roadmaps, no question practice, no community-driven interview insights
Glassdoor [8]	Company insights & reviews	Interview experiences, salary data, reviews	Real interview experiences	Unstructured content, no learning path or preparation resources

4. Results

4.1. Platform Feature Analysis

The comparative analysis of developer learning platforms reveals a clear pattern: each platform optimizes for a specific function rather than the end-to-end preparation journey. Coding platforms offer extensive problem sets and develop problem-solving skills but frequently assume prior conceptual knowledge, making them less accessible to beginners. Conceptual learning platforms are thorough in theory but lack practice integration. Community platforms provide authentic insight into real interview processes, yet the information is distributed and difficult to navigate. Roadmap platforms offer directional guidance but function primarily as static references rather than fully integrated systems.

A second observation is that most platforms contain quality content that remains disconnected from other preparation components. Users generally know what to study but face difficulty transitioning between learning stages. The identified gap is therefore not a lack of resources, but a lack of integration between them.

4.2. Key Observations from Platform Analysis

- Most platforms address only an individual part of the preparation process
- Users must rely on multiple platforms simultaneously
- No single platform covers the complete preparation workflow
- There is no continuous or integrated preparation flow across platforms

4.3. Survey Results: Fragmentation Validation

A preliminary survey of $N = 14$ users confirmed that platform fragmentation is a lived experience among learners. As shown in Figure 1 (Part A), 78.6% of respondents used three or more platforms simultaneously, with GeeksforGeeks (100%), LeetCode (78.6%), YouTube (75%), and roadmap.sh (75%) being the most commonly used. 64% reported switching platforms often or very often during a single session, and 64% agreed that this disrupted their focus. 78.6% found tracking progress across platforms to be difficult or very difficult.

1. How many platforms do you currently use to prepare for technical interviews?
14 responses

4. Does switching between multiple platforms break your focus or learning flow?
14 responses

2. Which platforms do you primarily use for interview preparation? (Select a)
14 responses

3. How often do you switch between different preparation platforms during a single study session?
14 responses

5. How difficult is it to track your overall preparation progress across all the platforms you use?
14 responses

Figure 1: user survey for current preparation habits and fragmentation experience

1. How long have you used NullSphere?
14 responses

4. Compared to your previous preparation method, NullSphere made preparation:
14 responses

3. Rate NullSphere on the following aspects (1 = Poor, 5 = Excellent)

2. Did NullSphere reduce your need to switch between other preparation platforms?
14 responses

5. Would you recommend NullSphere to someone preparing for technical interviews?
13 responses

Figure 2: user survey for nullsphere usage and comparison

1. What is your current professional or academic status?
14 responses

3. Which country are you primarily based in?
12 responses

2. How many years of professional or serious academic coding experience do you have?
14 responses

Figure 3: user demographic context

Open-ended responses consistently pointed toward consolidation as the primary unmet need, with participants noting needs such as "all material at one place" and "consistency, better knowledge at one place." These findings confirm that the fragmentation problem is not merely structural but directly impacts the learning experience.

4.4. NullSphere Deployment Metrics

To validate NullSphere as a publicly accessible and functional system, the platform was deployed and monitored using Google Analytics over a 28-day period from 7 March to 3 April 2026. During this period, the platform gained 200 active users and 191 new users, recording over 1,100 page views. The average engagement time per active user was 1 minute 20 seconds, indicating active interaction with the platform rather than immediate departure.

Traffic was received through multiple channels: direct visits accounted for the largest share (167 sessions), followed by Organic Social (96 sessions), Organic Search (25 sessions), and Referral (6 sessions). Users accessed the platform from six countries including India, the United States, the United Kingdom, South Korea, Nepal, and Sweden, demonstrating geographic reach beyond the initial target region.

Figure 4: User Traffic Metrics

5. Discussion

5.1. Interpretation of Findings

The results of both the platform analysis and the preliminary user survey corroborate the central thesis of this paper: the primary gap in the technical interview preparation ecosystem is not the absence of content, but the absence of integration. Each existing platform performs well within its own scope, yet the burden of connecting these resources falls entirely on the learner. This aligns with broader findings in e-learning research suggesting that cognitive load imposed by tool-switching and context-shifting negatively affects learning efficiency.

The survey findings, while preliminary due to the small sample size ($N = 14$), are consistent in direction. The high proportion of users relying on three or more platforms (78.6%), and the difficulty in tracking cross-platform progress (78.6%), suggests that fragmentation is a systemic issue rather than an individual preference. Future work with larger, randomized samples is needed to confirm these findings at statistical significance.

5.2. NullSphere as a Proposed Solution

NullSphere directly addresses the identified gap by consolidating preparation resources into a single integrated system. The 28-day deployment results, while limited in

scope, demonstrate that the platform is functional, publicly accessible, and able to attract users from multiple geographic regions and discovery channels. The average engagement time of 1 minute 20 seconds is indicative of active use, though longer-term engagement data would be needed to assess retention and learning outcomes.

The platform's current implementation covers the foundational modules of a unified preparation system. Advanced features including adaptive AI recommendations, expanded community tools, and deeper analytics are ongoing development priorities. The current work serves as a proof-of-concept for the integrated approach rather than a fully optimized system.

5.3. Limitations

Several limitations should be acknowledged. First, the user survey sample (N = 14) is small and was recruited exclusively from the platform's own user base, introducing selection bias. Second, the 28-day deployment window provides limited data on long-term user engagement or learning outcomes. Third, the platform evaluation methodology is qualitative and based on the researcher's personal usage experience, which may not capture all use cases. Fourth, the technical interview preparation ecosystem is rapidly evolving, and platform features may have changed since evaluation. Future studies should employ larger, controlled user studies with pre/post learning assessments to evaluate the effectiveness of the integrated approach.

6. Proposed Solution: NullSphere

6.1. Overview

NullSphere is developed as a one-stop platform for technical interview preparation. It consolidates learning resources, interview experiences, and roadmaps into a single system, reducing dependency on multiple platforms and making preparation more structured and focused.

6.2. Key Features

NullSphere integrates multiple components designed to support the end-to-end technical interview preparation process. Rather than treating learning, practice, and community interaction as separate activities, the platform unifies them into a structured workflow. Key features include:

- Roadmap-driven learning system with AI-powered personalized roadmap generation
- Curated learning resources aligned with structured learning paths
- Topic-wise question bank for focused and targeted preparation
- Interview experience repository enabling real-world scenario understanding
- Community interaction through comments, feedback, and content contribution

6.3. System Implementation

NullSphere is built as a full-stack application with monolithic architecture and clear separation between frontend and backend layers. Both layers are developed using TypeScript to maintain codebase consistency and reduce type-related errors. The frontend is implemented using Next.js [9], providing a responsive and structured interface. The backend

is implemented using Node.js with Express [13], organized into modular components including routers, controllers, models, middleware, and utilities.

The database layer uses MongoDB [10] with Mongoose [11] as the Object-Document Mapper. Authentication is implemented using JWT-based access tokens and refresh tokens, with third-party Google sign-in [15] supported. A common content lifecycle model is applied across all content types, including interview experiences, learning resources, and roadmaps, each following a draft-to-published flow with soft deletion support.

The AI-based roadmap generation feature allows users to generate personalized roadmaps based on topic and skill level by integrating with an external AI service. Responses are validated and stored using transactional database operations to ensure consistency. Form validation on the frontend is implemented using Zod [12] schema-based validation, improving input reliability prior to backend processing.

Figure 5: System Design(User Flow)

7. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that while several platforms offer valuable functionality, including coding practice, learning materials, interview experiences, and roadmaps, they operate as independent, disconnected systems. The primary issue is not a lack of content but a lack of integration across the preparation workflow.

The survey and deployment findings support the proposition that a unified platform can address this gap effectively. NullSphere is proposed as an integrated solution that brings together roadmaps, resources, question banks, interview experiences, and community

interaction within a single coherent system. The 28-day deployment provided preliminary evidence of user adoption and geographic reach, supporting the platform's viability as a unified interview preparation solution.

Future work will focus on expanding the user study with a larger and more diverse sample, implementing advanced adaptive recommendation features, and evaluating learning outcomes through pre/post assessment methodologies. The long-term goal is to establish NullSphere as a validated, research-backed platform for technical interview preparation.

8. Future Work

- AI Interviewing System: Simulated interview scenarios with performance feedback
- Chatbot Support: Integrated assistant to guide users through preparation stages
- Expanded Community Features: Advanced discussion mechanisms and contribution tracking
- Improved User Experience: Cleaner navigation and more intuitive interface design
- Larger User Study: Controlled evaluation with pre/post learning assessments

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